

EXAMINATION OF THE OPINIONS OF STUDENTS STUDYING AT THE FACULTY OF SPORTS SCIENCES ABOUT FAIRPLAY

Ender ÖZBEK,

Dr., Dicle University, School of Physical Education and Sports, endersozbek@gmail.com

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4348-5290

Fatma Beyza BİLGİÇ,

Dr., Batman Akşemsettin Girls Anatolian Imam Hatip High School, Ministry of Education,

beyza_44_@windowslive.com , ORCID ID: 0009-0000-0971-8818

ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın amacı, spor bilimleri fakültesinde okuyan öğrencilerin fair play hakkında görüşlerinin incelenmesidir. Çalışmada Efe (2006) tarafından geliştirilen ve 26 maddeden oluşan fair play ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Analizler SPSS 24 programı ile yapılmış olup analizler esnasında T testi ve Anova testi uygulanmıştır. Yapılan analizler sonucunda cinsiyetler ile fair play skorları arasında anlamlı bir fark bulunmadığı, yaş aralıkları ile fair play skorları arasında anlamlı bir fark bulunmadığı ve katılımcıların okuduğu bölüm ile fair play skorları arasında anlamlı fark bulunmadığı sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fair play, Sportmenlik, Spor bilimleri

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine the opinions of students studying at the faculty of sports sciences about fair play. The fair play scale, developed by Efe (2006) and consisting of 26 items, was used in the study. Analyzes were made with SPSS 24 program and T test and Anova test were applied during the analysis. As a result of the analysis, it was concluded that there was no significant difference between genders and fair play scores, that there was no significant difference between age ranges and fair play scores, and that there was no significant difference between the department the participants studied and fair play scores.

Key Words: Fair play, Sportsmanship, Sports sciences

1. INTRODUCTION

In sports, the morality is called fair play. It is for the athlete to obtain what he desires legitimately, in a pleasant competitive setting, without causing injury to his opponents, and for the public to participate in the sporting conflict with the same understanding. In a nutshell, it is genuine success. It is a sporting understanding in which not every way to win is regarded permissible, ambition is substituted by determination, and attitudes of tolerance emerge. (Esentürk, 2016).

Fair Play, which emphasizes fair and honest play in its most basic form, is the development of ethical and aesthetic aspects in sports, as well as the demonstration of virtuous behavior (Yıldıran, 2005).

Fair-Play is often defined by three definitions. It was originally used to mean "good game." It was then assessed as "the state of mind that will reveal a good game and the behavioral pattern that is appropriate for an athlete." It was later defined as "all the behaviors and attitudes that game participants must exhibit in order for a good game to emerge." Later, it came to be used to denote "general honesty" in sports, playgrounds, and social situations. (Kaya, 2011).

This study was carried out to investigate the perspectives of students who would graduate as sports professionals on fair play, which they should implement in their own life, set an example for, and pass on to the generations they will raise.

2. METHOD

The relational screening model was employed in this study. This model is a scan of the entire universe or a sample taken from it to arrive at a general judgment about the universe in a universe with a vast number of elements (Karasar, 2017).

The study included 203 students from Yozgat Bozok University's Faculty of Sports Sciences. A survey form created in Google Forms was used to collect data. The collected data was analyzed using the SPSS 24 program. 60.6% of the students participating in the research are male students and 39.4% are female students. 36.9% of the participants in the research are between the ages of 18-19, 31.5% are between the ages of 20-21 and 31.5% are over 21 years of age. Besides, 31.5% of the participants are studying in the Coaching department, 44.8% are studying in the Physical Education Teaching department, and 23.6% are studying in the Sports Management department.

Efe (2006) designed a 29-item measure that was employed in the study. It only has one dimension. Furthermore, because the results of the normality tests indicated a normal distribution, the T test and One Way Anova tests, both of which are parametric tests, were performed.

3. FINDINGS

Table 1: Analysis results comparing gender variable and fair play

	Gender	n	X± Sd	t	p
Fair play	Female	80	1,47±0,15	-1,361	0,17
	Male	123	1,45±0,14		

As a consequence of the analysis, it was specified that there was no significant difference in the average fair play scores between male and female genders. Additionally, it was determined that the averages of female students were higher than the averages of male students.

Table 2: Analysis results of comparison of age variable and fair play

	Age	n	X	sd	p	Tukey
Fair play	18-19 years old¹	75	1,42	0,15	0,47	
	20-21 years old²	64	1,43	0,16		
	21 years old³	64	1,45	0,13		

As a result of the analyses, it was determined that there was no significant difference between age ranges and fair play scores at the $p < 0.05$ level and the averages of the 21 and over age group were higher than the averages of other groups.

Table 3: Analysis results of comparison of department variable and fair play

	Department	n	X	Sd	p	Tukey
Fair play	Coaching¹	64	1,43	0,16	0,69	
	Physical Education and Sports²	91	1,41	0,16		
	Sports Management³	48	1,47	0,10		

As a result of the analysis, it was determined that there was no significant difference between the department the participants studied and their sports fair play scores, and the average fair play score of the students of the sports management department was higher than the others.

4. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

The investigation revealed that there was no significant variation in average fair play scores between male and female genders. Furthermore, it was discovered that female students' averages were higher than male students' averages.

Koç and Nas (2017) found no significant difference between gender and fair play behavior among secondary school pupils in their study. This research backs up the findings. However, Erdogan, Başaran, Körmükçü, and Adali (2016) discovered a substantial difference between female and male students' concept of fair play in their study. This finding contradicts the findings of our examination.

The results revealed that there was no statistically significant difference between age ranges and fair play ratings at the $p < 0.05$ level, and the averages of the 21 and over age group were higher than the averages of the other groups.

Kilci, Göktaş, and Özdayı Teke (2018) discovered that there was no significant difference between the age variable and the knowledge of fair play. This finding lends support to our research. However, there was a substantial difference between the age variable and the understanding of fair play in the study conducted by Yılmaz, Çelik, Koca, and Uzun (2017). This finding contradicts our findings.

As a result of the analysis, it was discovered that there was no significant difference between the department the participants studied and their sports fair play scores, and the students of the sports management department had a higher average fair play score than the rest.

The study "Examination of the Attitudes of School of Physical Education and Sports Students Towards Sportsmanship" conducted by Kilci, Göktaş, Özdayı Teke, (2018) found no

significant difference between the department the participants studied and the understanding of fair play. This finding offers support to our research.

As an outcome, there are studies in the literature that both support and contradict the findings of this study, and it is anticipated that the findings of this study will contribute to the literature.

REFERENCE

- Erdemli, A. (1996). İnsan, Spor ve Olimpizm. İstanbul: Sarmal Yayınevi.
- Esentürk, O. K., & Koç Y. (2016). Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin sportmenlik kavramına ilişkin görüşleri. 14th International Sport Sciences Congress, Antalya.
- Karasar, N. (2017). Bilimsel araştırma yöntemi: Kavramlar ilkeler teknikler. (32. Basım). Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- Kaya, S. (2011). İlköğretim okul yöneticilerinin, beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin ve öğrencilerinin okul spor programındaki fair play anlayışları: Bolu ili örneği. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Bolu.
- Kilci, A., Göktaş, Z., Özdayı, N. (2018). Beden Eğitimi Ve Spor Yüksekokulu Öğrencilerinin Sportmenliğe Yönelik Tutumlarının İncelenmesi Uluslar Arası Herkes İçin Spor Ve Wellness Kongresi. Antalya, 311
- Koç, Y., Artunç, M. (2017). Değerler Eğitiminde Sportmenlik Temasının İşlenmesinin Öğrencilerin Sportmenlik Davranışlarına Etkisi. 16. Uluslararası Spor Bilimleri Kongresi Antalya, 670.
- Koç, Y., Nas, H. (2017). Ortaokul Öğrencilerinin Öz-Yeterliklerinin Öğrencilerin Sportmenlik Davranışlarına Etkisi. 16. Uluslararası Spor Bilimleri Kongresi Antalya, 677.
- Yıldırım, İ. (2005). Fair play eğitiminde beden eğitiminin rolü. Gazi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, 10(1), 3-6.
- Yıldırım, İ. (2013). Fair play: An etymological, semantic and historical study. Play Fair! (Academic Supplement), 10 (1), 1-4.